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Sustainable Tourism Development In Petak Gianyar Village, Bali: Potentials And Challenges

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ABSTRACT

Petak Village, located in Gianyar, Bali, possesses great potential for agriculture-based tourism due to its rich nature and culture. The available tourism amenities include waterfalls, trekking paths, spiritual tourism, and other activities based on local wisdom. However, tourism in the village is still challenged by inadequate infrastructure, insufficient marketing, a lack of community participation in the management, and several other factors. This is the main reason this research is conducted, to uncover the tourism potential and challenges of Petak Village in the context of sustainable tourism. The employed strategy centres on qualitative methods with a descriptive approach which features observations, document analysis, and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with key stakeholders from the local community, village administration, and tourism entrepreneurs. Based on the focus group discussions, we found that Petak Village has significant opportunities to be further developed into a natural and cultural centre, which would enhance the enduring economic livelihoods of the residents. However, they lack sufficient regulations for effective tourism management, coordination among the myriad stakeholders, a workforce, stronger communities and other regional developmental bodies, the active collaboration of public sectors, and nurture for infrastructure. This study's conclusion verifies that the Petak Village sustainable tourism development shall consider the preservation of the environment, the well-being of the local community, and the area's economic activities in a unified manner involving all relevant participants.

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1. Introduction

Sustainable tourism is a strategic issue in managing tourist destinations, especially in areas with rural, natural, and cultural-based tourism potential. Bali, as one of the best tourist destinations in the world, has long been known for its cultural tourism features. However, in recent decades, the dominance of mass tourism has led to negative impacts such as the exploitation of natural resources, environmental degradation, and a shift in the socio-culture of local values (Andayani et al., 2017; Picard, 1990; Sutawa, 2012). As a result, developing community-based sustainable tourism, especially in integrating the economy, environment, and social welfare, is becoming increasingly important.

Petak Village in Gianyar Regency, Bali, is one of the villages with great potential for developing rural tourist destinations. Various tourist attractions are available in this village, such as waterfalls, trekking trails,

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spiritual tourism, and unique local culture. The concept of community-based and nature-based tourism management applied in Penglipuran, and Tenganan Villages (Putra, 2015; Lestari et al., 2024; Utama et al., 2024) proves that tourism management by local communities can improve their economic conditions and cultural preservation. However, infrastructure development in Petak Village is still constrained by promotion and lack of collaboration between stakeholders such as the government, the community, and tourism business actors.

The existence of local community members is the main requirement and must be in line with sustainable tourism policies (Fafurida et al., 2020; Lasso & Dahles, 2023). Petak Village can apply a community-based management model implemented in several villages in Southeast Asia as an alternative to tourism development to get social support and prioritize local and environmental values (Arintoko et al., 2020; Khadry & Sianipar, 2025).

Based on this background, identifying tourism potential and challenges in sustainable tourism development in Petak Village is the goal of this research. This research is qualitative research and uses data collection techniques in the form of observation and documentation, as well as Focus Group Discussions (FGD) to obtain information on destination management that, at the same time, preserves cultural and natural buildings to increase community income. The results of this research will likely provide input into the development of tourism villages in Bali, including the sustainable tourism model applied in Petak Village.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Previous Research

Susila & Putra (2022) offer a direct study of the tourism potential of Petak Village by analyzing natural, cultural, and artificial aspects. The uniqueness and richness of the tourism potential of Petak Village is the background of the problem that has not been managed optimally. The urgency comes from the fact that this potential is still at the level of introduction and management that is not integrated, so it has not provided maximum economic benefits for the community. This study aims to explore and document the potential of tourism using a qualitative approach involving observation, interviews, and documentation studies. The findings show that although Petak Village has vast potential, the level of resistance among the community and the lack of infrastructure facilities hinder tourism development. This study has similarities to your study regarding local potential, but differs in the descriptive nature of the observed phenomenon, while current study seeks to formulate a model of sustainable tourism development by examining management issues.

The research of Wisnawa et al., (2024) focuses on strengthening village resources through potential mapping and production of promotional videos for Plot Villages. The rationale for this study underscores the role of village potential mapping as a necessary stage in the effective promotion and development of tourism. The urgency is related to the need to capture information digitally and increase the attractiveness of promotions to market tourism potential more widely. The research aims to map the potential area of tourism and create promotional videos as an informative visual communication tool. The methods used include field observations, interviews with village council members, and collaboration with students within the framework of KKNT. The results show that mapping and video recording have increased awareness and interest in visiting, although there are still gaps in collaboration and management of promotional infrastructure. Compared to your research, this process has similarities in exploring the potential of Petak Villages. At the same time, this study focuses more on promotion and mapping as a short-term solution. In contrast, current research develops a more integrated approach involving community empowerment and environmental conservation programs.

Research by Srinadi et al., (2014) focuses on grouping villages in Gianyar Regency based on poverty factors. The background of this study is economic inequality in a village as a limitation that requires an adaptive approach to integrated rural development. The urgency of this research is based on the problem of understanding local economic conditions in order to design appropriate development policies. This

study aims to identify and classify villages in terms of poverty profile using secondary data from BPS and cluster analysis. The method used is quantitative with a statistical approach. It was found that there were significant differences between villages in poverty levels. Although the main focus is on the economic aspect, this study also provides an important context that socio-economic conditions in Gianyar significantly impact the potential for sustainable tourism development, in contrast to this research, which focuses on tourism integration and environmental conservation.

Musthofa (2019) studied development strategies and involved local communities in rural tourism. In the problem statement, it is explained that community involvement is essential to ensure the development of tourism that is economically beneficial and culturally sustainable. The importance of this research is the issue of community participation from the planning phase to the implementation of tourism development. These situations often hinder the success of rural tourism programs. To achieve this goal, the research seeks to find effective strategies that can increase community participation by using qualitative approaches such as observation and in-depth interviews. The results show that community participation is actively involved and can support the development of tourism villages, albeit with poor stakeholder coordination. This research focuses on participatory strategies, while the current ones are more comprehensive, including an analysis of tourism potential and management challenges.

Susyanti & Latianingsih (2015) studied the potential of villages through rural tourism as an alternative for poverty alleviation and cultural preservation. This study focuses on the richness of the unique nature and culture of villages that have not been optimally utilized to support the local economy. The urgency of this research arises from the need to optimize the potential for community empowerment and village tourism development. This study aims to assess the tourism potential in the village and develop an appropriate community empowerment model using a participatory approach. The methods include surveys, interviews, and field observations, which provide data on existing obstacles and potentials. The study's findings show that while there is great potential for tourism, the community's lack of understanding and preparedness is a barrier. The research has similarities in focusing on village potential but differs in that it emphasizes the empowerment dimension for poverty alleviation, while this research is about the development of sustainable tourism as an integrative model.

The research was conducted by (Putra et al., 2024) to digitize the potential of Petak Kaja Village by developing a village website. This initial research is based on the development of information technology that provides new opportunities for marketing and village tourism promotion activities. The importance lies in the need to increase the digital visibility of tourism potential, given the role of technology in optimizing tourist access to information. This research aims to create an OpenSID-based website and train village staff to be independent in creating tourism content. The methods applied are special, such as case studies, software development, and direct assistance to the field to village staff. The results of the study show that tourism promotion through digital means using websites is effective. However, it is recommended to continue to strengthen it in terms of content and management. In contrast to this research, which focuses on the development of holistic sustainable tourism, the research focuses more on aspects of digitalization and online promotion as one of the supporting components.

2.2. Sustainable Tourism

Sustainable tourism considers social sustainability, economic benefits, and environmental preservation at the same time (Zheng et al., 2023). This concept encourages stakeholders to manage tourism destinations in a way that does not harm the ecosystem while providing social and economic benefits to local communities. In other words, sustainable tourism means that residents are involved in the planning and executing tourism events to ensure sustainable economic benefits. Ecotourism also relies on the wise management of natural resources, including the preservation of natural habitats, carbon footprint reduction, and waste management. This concept also highlights the need for appropriate regulations to

protect the environment and stimulate economic development without excessive depletion of natural resources.

Sustainable tourism pays attention to environmental, economic, and social justice aspects simultaneously in developing a tourism area (Arida, 2016). The concept aims to ensure that tourism benefits communities and economies in the long term while minimizing environmental negative impacts. Sustainable tourism includes the promotion of social and economic justice, community involvement in destination planning and management, and responsible environmental management (Bausch et al., 2019). The same principle is applied to protect future tourism, communal well-being, quality of life and balance (Andrianto & Kusumah, 2021). Green tourism also prioritizes carbon emission reduction, waste management and the preservation of local culture (Simanungkalit & Sari, 2015).

2.3. Natural Resources for Tourism

The goal of natural resource management in tourism is to ensure that the exploitation of minerals will financially, socially, and environmentally support the region in the long term. Exploiting natural resources (SDA) in tourism includes conservative, rehabilitative, and prudent use that promotes the protection of nature and avoids the destruction of biodiversity, the main attraction of tourist destinations (Scuttari et al., 2023). Many issues directly related to tourism sustainability are connected to natural resource management (SDA), where poor management leads to degradation, such as coastal pollution or the destruction of coral reefs (Bausch et al., 2019). Ecotourism principles are useful for tourism planning and management because they minimize negative environmental impacts and empower local communities (WWF-Indonesia, 2009). This approach goes beyond conservation; this allows people to understand how to actively participate in managing sustainable and environmentally friendly tourism (Setyanti et al., 2021)

3. Methodology

This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach to analyse sustainable tourism development's potential and challenges in Petak Village, Gianyar, Bali. This approach allows for a deep understanding of the socio-economic and cultural conditions of the community in the context of a community-based tourism management system. This study is designed as an exploratory study that combines observation, documentation, and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) methods to collect rich and comprehensive data (Hennink, 2013; Hutter et al., 2020) on tourism management in Petak Village, conducted on Monday, 10 February 2025.

In this study, the population refers to all stakeholders involved in the tourism development of Petak Village, including local community members, village government representatives, local tourism entrepreneurs, and tourists. The sample, on the other hand, is a subset of this population selected based on purposive sampling techniques, where 20 key informants were interviewed. These informants included 10 local people, 5 representatives from the local government, and 5 local tourism entrepreneurs, chosen for their knowledge and involvement in tourism management within the village.

The Focus Group Discussion (FGD) conducted with stakeholders in Petak Village included a series of carefully designed questions to capture a broad range of perspectives regarding the potential and challenges of sustainable tourism development. The key questions addressed in the FGD were aimed at exploring the following aspects:

- 1) Tourism Potential and Community Engagement
 - a. What do you perceive as the main tourism assets in Petak Village (natural, cultural, and spiritual attractions)?
 - b. How do you think the local community can be more actively involved in the management and development of tourism in the village?
- 2) Challenges and Barriers

- a. What are the major challenges faced by the community and tourism operators in developing sustainable tourism?
- b. Are there any specific infrastructure or regulatory gaps that hinder the growth of tourism in Petak Village?
- 3) Environmental and Cultural Sustainability
 - a. How do you view the potential impact of tourism on the environment and local culture?
 - b. What measures do you think should be taken to ensure that tourism development aligns with environmental sustainability and cultural preservation?
- 4) Collaboration and Stakeholder Coordination
 - a. How would you rate the level of coordination among local stakeholders, including the government, local businesses, and the community?
 - b. What steps can be taken to enhance collaboration and create a more cohesive tourism management system?

These questions were designed to gain insights into the stakeholders' views and to better understand how to overcome the challenges and leverage the potential of Petak Village for sustainable tourism development. The findings from these discussions formed the basis for identifying key strategies for the village's tourism management.

This study uses primary and secondary data as sources for analysis. Primary data sources were collected through direct observation, in-depth interviews, and FGDs with stakeholders from tourism villages.

Various government policy documents on sustainable tourism in Bali, official village reports, and academic analyses are also taken as secondary data. The information was obtained in three main ways, namely field observations of tourist attractions and supporting infrastructure, village archive documents and policy reports, and FGDs with various stakeholders to discuss sustainable tourism development.

The data analysis in this study uses a thematic analysis method, where all data from interviews, observations, and documentation are categorized into certain themes relevant to the focus of the research (Hennink, 2013; Hutter et al., 2020). This process is carried out in three stages: data reduction to sort and simplify the information obtained, presentation of data in the form of narratives and thematic tables, and drawing conclusions to interpret the main results and relate them to sustainable tourism theories and policies in Bali.

From this analysis, basic information will be obtained regarding strategies in the development of Petak Village tourism as well as sustainable tourism models that are friendly to the community, the environment, and the tourism sector.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Results

Based on the results of the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and secondary data analysis of planning documents for the development of the tourism sector in Petak Village, it was found that this village has great potential for sustainable tourism development but, at the same time, faces significant challenges.

1. Tourism Potential in Petak Village

Petak Village has a variety of tourist attractions that can be further developed. The tourism potential is divided into three main categories: natural, cultural, and spiritual.

Table 1. Tourism Potential in Petak Village

Tourism Categories	Main Attraction
Nature Tourism	Air Terjun Toya Selaka, jalur trekking dan cycling, River Adventure Tracking, Hidden Canyon, Natural Swimming Pool

Cultural Tourism	Carvings, traditional dances, sculptures, and cultural attractions in the Bonyuh and Benawah areas
Spiritual Tourism	Pura Gunung Mertha, Pesiraman Tirta Sudamala, Pura Puncak Sari, Pura Dalem Suci

The diversity of these attractions provides a substantial opportunity for Petak Village to be developed as a Community-Based Tourism (CBT) destination. This model has proven successful in several tourist villages in Bali, such as Penglipuran and Tenganan (Putra, 2015; Lestari et al., 2024; Utama et al., 2024).

2. Challenges in Sustainable Tourism Development

Although it has great potential, there are several challenges in the development of Petak Village tourism, as summarized in the following table

Table 2. Tourism Potential in Petak Village

Factor	Description
Strength	Petak Village possesses significant strengths for sustainable tourism development, primarily its rich natural resources, including waterfalls, trekking paths, and spiritual sites, alongside a vibrant cultural heritage. These assets create a strong foundation for tourism activities, supported by the active involvement of the local community in managing tourism through the Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis). This community participation ensures that the economic benefits of tourism stay within the village while promoting cultural preservation and environmental sustainability.
Weaknesses	Lack of information and socialization regarding the benefits of tourism, lack of clear regulatory support, community resistance related to private land use, lack of community skills in tourism management
Opportunities	Petak Village has several promising opportunities to enhance its tourism sector, including the potential for expanding the Community-Based Tourism (CBT) model, which could empower locals to manage tourism sustainably and benefit economically. Additionally, improving infrastructure like eco-friendly trekking routes, waste management, and accommodations would increase the village's appeal. Strengthening stakeholder collaboration, leveraging digital marketing for broader promotion, and hosting cultural events are all opportunities that could boost the village's visibility and contribute to its sustainable tourism development
Threats	The risk of environmental damage due to mass tourism, disruption to the sanctity of places of worship (Parhyangan), uncontrolled socio-cultural

	changes (Pawongan), and lack of regulations in tourism management (Palemahan)
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Based on the experience of developing tourist villages in Bali, such as Jatiluwih, Tenganan, and Penglipuran (Sardiana et al., 2017; Sri Budhi & Lestari, 2016), the main problem that often arises is community resistance due to concerns about losing land rights. Therefore, a partnership-based approach and education are urgently needed.

4.2. Discussion

1. Implementation of Community-Based Tourism (CBT) Model

The Community-Based Tourism (CBT) model allows local communities to actively manage tourism in their area so that the local economy benefits in addition to investors (Fafurida et al., 2020; Lasso & Dahles, 2023). This model seeks to ensure sustainable tourism by involving communities in every phase of planning, managing, and implementing tourism activities (Zheng et al., 2023). Previous research has shown that implementing CBT in several rural tourism villages in Bali, such as Penglipuran Village and Tenganan Village, has improved the welfare of local communities and supported the preservation of local culture (Andayani et al., 2017; Chevalier et al., 2019; Lestari et al., 2024; Arini et al., 2023). Not only do people who participate in tourism management receive economic benefits, but they also become stakeholders in tourist destinations, which encourages them to actively participate in the conservation of the environment and culture of the area (Beeh, 2017; Junaid et al., 2021; Nugroho & Harrison, 2021; Tolkach & King, 2015). Therefore, the implementation of CBT in Petak Village can function to improve the welfare of the community while preserving local wisdom. One of the steps taken in implementing CBT in Petak Village is establishing a Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis), which is the main manager of community-based tourist destination areas. Pokdarwis plans offer various tour packages and maintain the balance of the ecosystem in its implementation so that the community as a whole can enjoy the economic services offered as a result of the development of tourism activities that have emerged in the Village (Prasiasa et al., 2020). In addition, establishing an organized and active Pokdarwis is also expected to build connections with decision-makers such as local governments, investors, and academics to expand support in community-based tourism management. With the existence of the Pokdarwis, tourism management in Petak Village can be better and more sustainable.

In addition to establishing Pokdarwis, community education and training are also important aspects of implementing CBT. Training can cover various areas such as tourism management, hospitality services, digital marketing, and active practices for environmental conservation (Musthofa, 2019). Previous research revealed that tourism villages that successfully implemented CBT, such as Munduk and Tembi, had residents who were given advanced training to enable self-managed tourism efforts (Sutawa, 2012). There is a need for education to increase public awareness regarding the need to maintain ecological and cultural sustainability in the scope of tourism (Andrianto & Kusumah, 2021). So, in Petak village, a training program involving academics, local governments, and non-governmental organizations is designed to improve the residents' skills and readiness to manage tourism professionally.

In addition to training, the partnership model in the form of a profit-sharing system or land lease can also answer people's fears related to land ownership. In Munduk Village, this system has been successfully implemented where community-owned land is, in principle, managed by an investor or tourism operator through a profit-sharing system (Sutawan, 2010). In this way, people do not lose land ownership but receive economic benefits from tourism activities. A similar approach can be applied in Petak Village if there is a clear policy regarding the partnership relationship between the community and tourism business actors. In addition, village tourism cooperatives can be established to manage tourism autonomously while still inviting investors as strategic partners (Bausch et al., 2019).

As a result of the Focus Group Discussion (FGD), as part of this study, it was found that community involvement in managing tourism in Petak Village is still limited due to inadequate regulations and lack of coordination among stakeholders. One of the main challenges is the lack of public understanding of the long-term economic benefits of sustainable tourism (Zheng et al., 2023). Therefore, implementing the CBT model requires active participation from the community and support from local governments in the form of clear regulations and continuous guidance (Simanungkalit & Sari, 2015). With a systematic and participatory approach, Petak Village has the potential to develop into a community-based tourism village that provides balanced economic, social, and environmental benefits.

2. Implementation of Community-Based Tourism (CBT) Model

In developing tourism infrastructure, it is very important to balance ecology and local wisdom (Bausch et al., 2019). In sustainable tourism, the lack of proper management of certain infrastructure can have negative impacts, such as environmental degradation, water resource pollution, and the loss of local culture (Zheng et al., 2023). Petak Village, which has rich natural and cultural tourism potential, faces problems related to the limited supporting infrastructure for sustainable tourism. The results of this study show that the lack of adequate supporting tourism facilities, such as environmentally friendly trekking trails, waste management, and eco-lodge accommodation, is the main obstacle to the development of tourist villages. Therefore, an environment-based approach to developing infrastructure must be implemented to ensure that the growth of the tourism industry does not harm the ecosystem and the sustainability of the village's natural resources. One example of infrastructure development that can be applied in Petak Village is the construction of natural trekking and cycling paths made of geosynthetic materials.

Both Penglipuran and Jatiluwih villages in Bali are examples of ecosites where this model is applied in Bali with eco-impact tour routes (Sardiana et al., 2017; Sri Budhi & Lestari, 2016). Well-executed trekking trails have the potential to provide a highly immersive and authentic tourism experience while simultaneously preserving the natural environment by minimizing the carbon footprint that tourism leaves behind. In addition, bicycle lanes also increase the concept of low-emission tourism, which is increasingly popular among tourists who care about the environment (Andrianto & Kusumah, 2021). Therefore, implementing environmental tourism routes in Petak Village can be part of the solution to develop sustainable, eco-friendly tourism in the area.

In addition to the marked path, the development of glamping accommodation and eco homestays is also a strategy to increase the attractiveness of tourism in this area while remaining environmentally friendly. Glamping, or luxury camping, is a new concept that has successfully found its place in natural tourism destinations in Indonesia. It attracts tourists who want to experience outdoor living in modern comforts but sustainably (Bausch et al., 2019). In Petak Village, the construction of glamping facilities can be done using natural materials and designs that blend in with the landscape to avoid and reduce the exploitation of natural resources.

Ecotourism-based homestays are one of the alternatives to increase community participation in the tourism sector by making accommodations under the principles of sustainability and local culture (Setyanti et al., 2021). Therefore, Petak Village can be built with environmentally friendly tourism infrastructure to achieve its goal as a community-based tourist destination that balances development and conservation.

In addition to tourist routes, accommodation accompanied by waste management and water resource conservation is also a crucial aspect of environment-based development. The results of the WWF-Indonesia study (2009) state that effective waste management in tourist villages must include public education about plastic waste reduction, the implementation of good waste treatment systems and green technology in waste management. Even though it is located in a rural area, implementing a community-based waste management system in Jatiluwih has been proven to reduce environmental pollution caused by tourism activities there (Sardiana et al., 2017; Sri Budhi & Lestari, 2016). With steps to build facilities and infrastructure in the form of environmentally friendly garbage cans and recycle bins, Petak

Village can do the same thing. Protecting water reserves and implementing sustainable irrigation systems also need to be held to ensure a clean water supply for the community and the tourism sector (Scuttari et al., 2023).

By the relevant literature, the development of sustainable tourism infrastructure requires social, economic, and environmental strategies to be well aligned (Zheng et al., 2023; Prasiasa & Widari, 2019; Widari, 2020; Widari, 2022). The impact of sustainable infrastructure goes beyond simply reducing the environmental burden. It also positively impacts the well-being of local communities by enabling their active participation in the management of tourism facilities (Simanungkalit & Sari, 2015). Integrating an environmental approach allows the village to maintain its natural appeal without causing ecosystem damage while developing a sustainable community-based tourism model in the village. Thus, there is a need for synergy between local governments, residents, and tourism entrepreneurs to develop ecotourism infrastructure that supports sustainable development integrated with regional ecosystems.

3. Partnership Model in Tourism Management

The main concern for tourism development in Petak Village is the local community's rejection against the use of private land for tourism development purposes. Based on interviews conducted with residents, there are concerns that the tourism development plan will result in the loss of land ownership to outsiders who will take advantage of the benefits unfairly at the expense of the villagers. This problem has also been noted in several other tourist villages. Therefore, what is needed is a development model based on partnerships that allow communities to have control over land while still providing economic benefits from tourism development. With existing partnerships, communities may be willing to accept tourism development in villages without sacrificing land ownership.

One of the partnership models that will be developed in Petak Village is based on long-term land leases with fair profit-sharing allocations for local communities. This has become a practice in other tourist villages where community-owned land remains community-owned but is managed by tourism entrepreneurs on a profit-sharing basis (Setyanti et al., 2021). Through this approach, communities can earn passive income from renting out land while maintaining ownership.

In addition, this scheme can also be combined with Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Programs from business actors for infrastructure development at the village level and Community Development Programs (Andrianto & Kusumah, 2021). If implemented with clear and transparent regulations, this partnership-based rental system could reduce public rejection of tourism development.

In addition to land leases, another partnership model that can be applied is establishing tourist village cooperatives. This cooperative functions as an institution that manages tourism businesses independently, with financial support from strategic partner investors. The cooperative model has been successfully implemented in several tourist villages in Indonesia, such as in Nglanggeran, where village cooperatives manage community-based tourism projects and community participation in managing tourists, including accommodation and entrance tickets (Bausch et al., 2019). Through cooperatives, communities can earn more income from available resources because they directly control tourism operations in the village. Cooperatives also play a significant role in ensuring that the principles of sustainability and cultural heritage are well maintained as the main focus in developing tourism in Petak Village. The success of this partnership model depends largely on well-defined regulations and the effective socialization of local communities.

As a result of the Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) held for this study, it was found that most of the community, in this case, the farmers, are still unaware of how the partnership model can provide economic benefits without infringing on their land tenure. That is why local governments play an important role in formulating and providing supporting regulations to protect local communities in the partnership system legally (Zheng et al., 2023). In addition to regulations, the government should also focus on implementing education and socialization programs that will help community members understand the partnership

mechanism and the long-term benefits that can be generated from community-based tourism development.

With the right partnership system, Petak Village can develop sustainable tourism without the dichotomy of community versus business conflicts. The area of sociological research includes the economic relationship between governments and non-profit cooperatives. The profit-sharing land lease model and rural tourism cooperatives are the means of tourism development in these villages while achieving balance in the sociological, economic, and environmental domains (Simanungkalit & Sari, 2015). In addition, a combination bottom-up approach results from the community, ensuring that local communities remain in primary control over managing their village tourism. For this reason, there is a need to combine the actions of local communities, local governments, and capitalists to create a fair, open, and sustainable partnership system.

4. Strengthening the Promotion and Branding of Petak Village as a Tourism Village

Digital marketing strategies are recognized globally as the most advanced way to show the advantages of a particular place. Promotion is one of the key elements for developing tourist villages because it can increase the profile of the destination and attract a larger number of tourists. With the advent of technology, modern marketing strategies have proven to be one of the most efficient ways to sell an area's tourism (Putra et al., 2023). Previous studies have found that tourist villages with an established digital promotion system tend to receive more visitors than those relying on traditional promotion methods (Mahesa Putra et al., 2023). Petak Village is one of the few places that offers a variety of cultural and natural attractions. However, it still faces challenges in terms of promotion, especially in digital media and marketing technology. For this reason, the right branding strategy, along with digital technology, is the best answer to improve the position of Petak Village as a sustainable tourism destination.

Wisnawa et al. (2024) claim that social media and public websites can be one of the most important tools to promote local tourist attractions with a primary focus on the Plot area. Pedersen et al. (2023) propose that promotional tools such as Instagram and Facebook can reach international tourists and increase the area's exposure. In addition, the village's official website serves as an information portal for tourists interested in learning about travel packages, accommodation facilities, and cultural attractions available in the area. Tourism managers can now build direct interactions with potential visitors through social media and customer service features on the website. With an effective digital marketing strategy, Desa Petak can attract tourists more easily without relying on expensive traditional marketing tactics.

In addition to social media and websites, collaboration with travel agencies and other digital platforms is equally important in promoting Plot Village. A study by Wisnawa et al. (2024) highlights that partnerships with Traveloka, Airbnb, and Klook allow for greater exposure to market travel and lodging packages. Through this platform, tourists can easily access relevant information about the accommodation, growing tourist attractions, and unique experiences offered in Pekan Village. Additionally, partnerships with travel agencies are beneficial in developing engaging tour packages that combine unique educational, ecotourism, and cultural experiences. Through this collaboration, Petak Tourism Village can reach a broader tourism market and significantly increase the number of tourist visits. In addition to digital strategies and partnerships with travel agencies, organizing local events and festivals is one of the most effective ways to promote a tourist village.

Research conducted by Putra et al. (2023) shows that festivals and cultural events can be a significant point of interest for tourists looking for an authentic experience in a destination. In other tourist villages such as Penglipuran Village and Tenganan Village, the implementation of cultural festivals has been proven to increase the number of tourist visits and strengthen the local community's identity. Therefore, Petak Village might consider hosting an annual event highlighting the village's culture, traditional arts, and culinary specialities to attract potential tourists. In addition to increasing tourism, this event will be a marketing opportunity for local products and creative businesses in the village.

Through strategic digital marketing, collaboration with travel agents, and organising local events, Petak Village has great potential to become a leading tourist village in Bali. A literature review shows that tourist villages that use digital marketing strategies, coupled with strong branding, achieve greater success in attracting visitors and improving the economic well-being of the local population (Simanungkalit & Sari, 2015). Based on the above findings, there is a need for local governments and residents to actively participate in promoting the village and improving the branding of the Petak community as a community-based sustainable tourism destination. Through a creative and integrated promotion strategy, Petak Village can certainly improve its position as one of the tourist attractions that are not only in demand by tourists but also able to strive to preserve the local environment and culture.

5. Conclusion

The development of Sustainable Tourism in Petak Village needs to present a strategy combining the implementation of CBT (Community Tourism) as the basis for development, eco-building, fair partnerships, and brand strengthening and promotion for village tourism.

To effectively address the practical implications of Sustainable Tourism Development (STD) in Petak Village, it is essential to propose more detailed strategies that ensure the growth of tourism while preserving local culture, the environment, and community livelihoods. A key strategy for Petak Village is the implementation of Community-Based Tourism (CBT), which will empower the local community to actively participate in the management and decision-making processes related to tourism. This model not only ensures that the economic benefits of tourism remain within the village but also mitigates concerns about land ownership loss. In practice, Petak Village could facilitate training programs for local residents in hospitality, guiding, and tourism management, helping them develop skills to manage tourism enterprises independently. Furthermore, the development of eco-friendly infrastructure, such as sustainable accommodations, waste management systems, and environmentally conscious trekking trails, is crucial. These initiatives would reduce the environmental impact of tourism while enhancing the village's appeal to eco-conscious tourists. To address the concerns of local communities regarding the possible negative impacts of tourism development, the establishment of fair partnership models, such as land lease agreements or profit-sharing arrangements, can provide economic benefits to the villagers without compromising their land ownership rights. This approach should be accompanied by the creation of village tourism cooperatives that enable the local community to retain control over tourism-related activities. Additionally, to increase Petak Village's visibility and attract sustainable tourism, a robust digital marketing strategy should be adopted. Collaborations with online travel platforms, social media influencers, and local tour operators will help promote the village's attractions to a global audience. Finally, organizing cultural events and festivals will not only highlight the unique cultural heritage of the village but also foster a deeper connection between tourists and the local community, making tourism development in Petak Village both economically and socially beneficial. By combining these strategies, Petak Village can position itself as a model for sustainable tourism, ensuring long-term benefits for both the environment and the community.

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